

Morphological changes in rice shoot due to excess water.^a Cuttack, India, 1980 wet season.

Variety	Treatment	Dry weight/tiller (g)			Leaf area/tiller (cm ²)		Specific leaf wt (mg/cm ²)		Crop growth rate (g/m ² per d)		
		20 DAS	Flowering	Maturity	20 DAS	Flowering	20 DAS	Flowering	20-45 DAS	45 DAS to flowering	Flowering to maturity
Janaki	Normal	0.76	2	4.30	75.3	41	2.70	7	5.6	11.6	4.0
	Submerged	0.72	3	4.43	52.8	101	5.43	6	5.8	12.8	4.2
CR1030	Normal	0.76	3	4.96	91.8	73	3.25	7	10.1	12.1	4.5
	Submerged	0.79	4	5.96	57.6	90	5.23	7	8.4	14.4	3.2
FR13-A	Normal	0.78	2	4.47	84.6	60	4.35	7	7.2	11.6	3.6
	Submerged	0.80	3	6.43	52.6	65	5.03	7	4.6	16.6	2.9
CN643	Normal	0.46	2	3.57	78.0	61	2.54	6	4.5	3.3	1.1
	Submerged	3.35	3	6.14	18.6	68	4.53	6	3.8	6.0	6.5
IET6205	Normal	0.73	2	5.67	96.3	56	2.93	7	8.8	6.9	3.6
	Submerged	0.53	4	7.20	45.8	94	4.56	8	7.7	12.5	5.8
IET6207	Normal	0.74	3	4.60	100.0	72	2.98	7	7.0	8.8	5.3
	Submerged	0.42	4	4.74	31.5	78	4.83	8	6.3	6.8	6.4
CR260-131	Normal	0.68	3	5.32	103.3	101	2.68	7	9.2	12.3	1.8
	Submerged	0.36	4	6.56	24.8	94	4.20	7	0.8	15.3	1.1
Mahsuri	Normal	0.59	1	3.33	81.4	40	2.60	6	10.6	1.4	9.9
	Submerged	0.64	4	3.73	52.2	90	4.90	7	1.1	11.0	8.1
IET6271	Normal	0.59	3	3.80	91.2	68	2.68	6	8.2	9.2	1.2
	Submerged	0.33	3	4.30	24.4	64	4.46	6	2.3	6.0	2.7
Jagannath	Normal	0.60	2	2.90	85.3	55	2.90	6	8.2	9.7	2.4
	Submerged	0.25	2	3.75	15.1	44	3.70	6	0.3	4.8	3.0
Mean	Normal	0.67	2	4.15	88.7	63	2.87	7	8.0	8.7	3.7
	Submerged	0.51	4	5.42	37.6	79	4.70	7	4.1	10.6	5.0
LSD (0.05)	Treatment	0.05	0.1	0.50	5.0	6	0.29	ns	1.2	1.4	1.0
	Variety	0.11	1.0	1.03	11.2	12	ns	1	2.7	3.2	1.5
	T×V	0.16	1.8	1.45	15.9	18	ns	ns	ns	4.5	ns

^aDAS = days after submergence.

Adverse soils tolerance

A rapid screening technique for salt tolerance in rice

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We screened 34 rice varieties for salt tolerance at germination and at the seedling stage. The effects of level of salinity and stage of salinization on rice growth were studied separately.

For seedling stage screening, 14-d-old seedlings were transplanted to Yoshida nutrient solution salinized incrementally with NaCl to concentrations of 0, 50, 100, 150, and 200 mol for 2 wk. Fresh and dry weight and percentage mortality were the criteria for assessing tolerance. The experiment was repeated with 16

varieties and with 7 varieties selected out of the 16.

Results of the solution culture studies were compared with those of soil culture

in pots (nine varieties). The solution culture technique was fairly reliable; the patterns of salt tolerance in various varieties, especially for the most tolerant and most sensitive, were the same in pot culture and in the field (see table).

Fresh and dry shoot weights were compared after 2 wk in solution. The

Salt tolerance of rice varieties at different growth stages.^a Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Variety or line	Germination	Salt-tolerance rating					Final
		Seedling stage ^b experiment			Maturity ^c		
		I	II	III	Pot trial	Field trial	
Basmati 370	MS	S	S	S	S	S	S
Basmati 198	MS	MS	MS	MS	MT	S	MS
NIAB6	T	T	T	T	T	T	T
IR6	T	MT	MT	T	MT	T	T
KS282	T	MT	MS	MT	MT	T	T
BG402-4	MT	T	T	MT	S	S	MS
IR1561	S	S	S	S	S	S	S

^a Tolerance class: S = sensitive, MS = moderately sensitive, MT = moderately tolerant, T = tolerant

^b Fresh and dry shoot weight and % maturity. ^c Yield basis.

solution technique had a significant correlation among the three experiments, showing high consistency and reproducibility of the technique.

Similarity with the results with pot culture and close association with field results (where absolute yields were the indices of salt tolerance) show the

practical validity of this technique.

The technique is simple, quick, and reliable for screening a large number of genotypes. □

Relationship of rice embryo weight and salinity tolerance at seedling stage

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We screened 19 indica and 6 japonica cultivars with varying embryo weights for salt tolerance, using water culture in the IRRI phytotron glasshouse (29/21 °C (day/ night) temperature, 70% relative humidity, natural daylight). Salinity stress of 6800 ppm (EC 12 dS/m) was introduced by adding 1:1 mixture of NaCl and CaCl₂ to the nutrient solution. Seedling survival after 2 wk salinization was taken as the criterion for salt tolerance.

Embryo weight/50 seeds ranged from 0.0140 g (Intan Gawri and Palman 46)

Correlation ($r = 0.2151^{ns}$) between embryo weight and seedling survival after 14 d salinization (EC = 12 dS/m). IRRI, 1989.

Cultivar	Embryo weight (g)	Survival (%)
Rikuto Norin 15	0.0467	7
Bombilla	0.0454	36
Chang You Zae Rae	0.0450	10
Thatnosubnet	0.0440	12
Jinbu 4	0.0393	45
Pokkali	0.0386	85
Nona Bokra	0.0358	89
IR51491-AC4-6	0.0309	90
IR31779-19-3-3-2-2	0.0302	10
RNR1429	0.0299	18
IR51491-AC4-7	0.0297	82
IR51500-AC9-8	0.0272	32
TNAU (AD) 103	0.0263	8
MI-48	0.0245	2
Khao youth	0.0237	22
IR25924-92-1-3	0.0236	5
Laxmi	0.0227	8
IR28	0.0226	20
Suweon 341	0.0219	70
IR36	0.0209	42
NIAB6	0.0208	25
Duansan	0.0202	18
Basmati 370	0.0195	20
Intan Gawri	0.0140	8
Palman 46	0.0140	2

to 0.0467 g (Rikuto Norin 15). Seedling survival under salinity stress ranged from 2 (Palman 46) to 90 (IR51491-AC4-6).

Among the cultivars studied, the

association between embryo weight and salt tolerance was not significant ($r = 0.2151$) (see table). This finding does not support earlier reports of such an association. □

Ion transport in two rice varieties grown under saline conditions

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Resistance to salt entry into the shoot is often related to survival and growth of plant species. We studied the transport of Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ from root to shoot in two rice varieties with different salt tolerances.

NIAB6 (salt tolerant) and IR1561 (salt sensitive) were transplanted at 14 d after seeding into Yoshida nutrient solution. Two salinity levels (0 and 100 mol NaCl) were used. Samples were taken at 7, 14, and 28 d after salinization. Cell sap of whole shoot and root was analyzed and rate of ion transport calculated as

$$J = (M_2 - M_1) / (\overline{WR} \times \Delta T)$$

where M_1 and M_2 are amounts of ion in samples 1 and 2, respectively; $\overline{WR}$ is the log mean root fresh weight (g); and T is difference between harvests, in days.

Rate of Na⁺ transport from root to shoot increased with salinity during both growth periods, but was higher 14 d after salinization (see table).

IR1561 had four times higher Na⁺ transport rate (J_{Na^+}) than NIAB6.

J_{K^+} decreased considerably from 14 to 28 d under no salinity and under 100 mol salinity. At 100 mol salinity, the drop in K⁺ transport (J_{K^+}) in salt-sensitive IR1561 was spectacular.

Rate of ion transport from root to shoot in 2 rice varieties under 2 salinity levels (0 [control] and 100 mol NaCl). Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Variety	7-14 d		14-28 d	
	0 (control)	100	0 (control)	100
<i>Rate of Na⁺ transport (μmol/g dry wt per d)</i>				
NIAB6	6.0	26.1	2.2	23.7
IR1561	9.2	106.1	1.7	17.9
<i>Rate of K⁺ transport (μmol/g dry wt per d)</i>				
NIAB6	235.4	98.7	80.2	45.3
IR1561	325.4	193.2	78.1	5.9
<i>Rate of Cl⁻ transport (μmol/g dry wt per d)</i>				
NIAB6	30.1	76.6	15.3	26.8
IR1561	37.1	170.2	16.4	33.9

IR1561 had higher J_{K^+} during early stress, but could not maintain the rate of K⁺ transport.

J_{Cl^-} was also much lower for NIAB6 than for IR1561, particularly during the first growth period. It decreased substantially during the second growth period, although it was still higher for IR1561 than for NIAB6. Lower J_{Cl^-} for NIAB6 at high salinity at 14 and 28 d after treatment indicates it has a better Cl⁻ exclusion mechanism.

Zinc:phosphorus ratio — a criterion for salt tolerance in rice

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Different physiological parameters (potassium selectivity [K:Na ratio], exclusion/ inclusion of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ in